

Effects of polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics on androgen- and estrogen receptor activity and steroidogenesis *in vitro*

Jeske van Boxel^{a,*}, Rani R.J. Khargi^a, Sandra M. Nijmeijer^a, Manuel T. Heinzelmann^b, Daniel Da Costa Pereira^c, Marja H. Lamoree^b, Majorie B.M. van Duursen^a

^a Amsterdam Institute for Life and Environment, section Environmental Health and Toxicology, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^b Amsterdam Institute for Life and Environment, section Chemistry for Environment and Health, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^c Division of Molecular and Computational Toxicology, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Dr. P Jennings

Keywords:

Endocrine disruption
Steroidogenesis
Polystyrene
Micro- and nanoplastics
Estrogen receptor
Androgen receptor

ABSTRACT

While many plastic additives show endocrine disrupting properties, this has not been studied for micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) particles despite their ubiquitous presence in humans. The objective of this study was to determine the effects of various sizes and concentrations of polystyrene (PS)-MNPs (50–10,000 nm, 0.01–100 µg/mL) on estrogen- and androgen receptor (ER and AR) activity and steroidogenesis *in vitro*. Fluorescent (F)PS-MNPs of ≤1000 nm were internalized in VM7 and H295R cells and FPS-MNPs ≤200 nm in AR-ecoscreen cells. H295R cells displayed the highest uptake and particles were closer to the nucleus than other cell types. None of the sizes and concentrations PS-MNPs tested affected ER or AR activity. In H295R cells, PS-MNPs caused some statistically significant changes in hormone levels, though these showed no apparent concentration or size-dependent patterns. Additionally, PS-MNPs caused a decrease in estriol (E3) with a maximum of 37.5 % (100 µg/mL, 50 nm) and an increase in gene expression of oxidative stress markers GPX1 (1.26-fold) and SOD1 (1.23-fold). Taken together, our data show limited endocrine-disrupting properties of PS-MNPs *in vitro*. Nevertheless the importance of E3 in the placenta warrants further studies in the potential effects of MNPs during pregnancy.

1. Introduction

Over the past century, global plastic production has shown a substantial increase, rising from 2 million metric tons (Mt) to 380 Mt. in 2015, with further growth anticipated (Geyer et al., 2017). Plastics are comprised of monomers, with polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyvinylchloride (PVC), and polystyrene (PS) among the most used varieties (Geyer et al., 2017). Additionally, plastics incorporate various additives and processing aids (Wiesinger et al., 2021). Bisphenols and phthalates, for instance, are additives included in plastics as hardeners and softeners, respectively. Plastics find application across numerous sectors, including packaging (Yates et al., 2021), plastic toys (Aurisano

et al., 2021) and plastic bags (Suleman et al., 2022). Strikingly, approximately 75 % of all plastics produced ultimately find its way into the environment, where it undergoes degradation leading to the formation of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), *i.e.* plastic particles that are less than 5 mm in diameter (Oliveira et al., 2020; Rubin, 2011). These MNPs can arise from thermal destruction, UV radiation, photo-degradation, and biodegradation, constituting secondary MNPs. Furthermore, primary MNPs are intentionally manufactured and used for example as abrasives in cosmetics and personal care products (Bashir et al., 2021; Dąbrowska et al., 2022).

MNPs vary in polymer type, chemical composition, and size. The presence of MNPs has been confirmed in various locations worldwide

Abbreviations: AR, Androgen receptor; AREs, Androgen response elements; CHO, Chinese Hamster Ovary; CYP, Cytochrome P450; DEHP, Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; DHEA, Dehydroepiandrosteron; DHT, Dihydrotestosterone; EDCs, Endocrine disrupting chemicals; ER, Estrogen receptor; E1, Estrone; E2, Estradiol; E3, Estriol; FBS, Fetal bovine serum; F, Fluorescent; FPS-MNPs, Fluorescent polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics; GD, Guidance document; GR, Glucocorticoid receptor; ICI, ICI182780; IS, Internal standard; KO, Knock-out; MNPs, Micro- and nanoplastics; MPs, Microplastics; Mt, Million metric tons; NIEHS, National Institute of Environmental Health; PE, Polyethylene; PP, Polypropylene; PS, Polystyrene; PVC, Polyvinylchloride; P/S, Penicillin Streptomycin; RFUs, Relative fluorescent units; RLUs, Relative light units; T, Testosterone; TG, Test guideline; UPW, Ultra-purified water; 3β-HSD, 3β-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase; 17αE2, 17-α-estradiol; 17βE2, 17-β-estradiol; 17β1-HSD, 17β1-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase.

* Corresponding author at: Amsterdam Institute for Life and Environment, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, P.O. box, The Netherlands.

E-mail address: j.van.boxel@vu.nl (J. van Boxel).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2024.105938>

Received 12 July 2024; Received in revised form 27 August 2024; Accepted 3 September 2024

Available online 5 September 2024

0887-2333/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell culture conditions

The VM7Luc4E2 cells (from now on called VM7 cells) were established and kindly provided by Prof. Dr. Rogers and Prof. Dr. Denison (Rogers and Denison, 2000). All the materials below were obtained from Gibco, unless stated otherwise. DMEM/F:12 (1:1) + GlutaMAX™-I medium supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1 % P/S and 40 µL Geneticin (50 mg/mL, CAS no. 108321-42-2) per 75cm² flask was used as growth medium while DMEM (1×) [+]₁ g/L D-glucose Pyruvate medium supplemented with 5 % DCS FBS and 1 % P/S was used as assay medium. AR-ecoscreen cells were designed from CHO-K1 cells (Satoh et al., 2004). These cells were obtained from the Japanese Collection of Research Bioresources Cell bank (Ibaraki city, Osaka) and improved for androgen specificity with a glucocorticoid receptor (GR) knockout (Zwart et al., 2017). The improved cells were the AR-ecoscreen GR KO cells (passage no. 4, from now on called AR-ecoscreen cells) and were cultured in the same medium as the VM7 cells, however, it was supplemented with 20 µL Zeonic (ThermoFisher, Cat. No. R25001) instead of Geneticin. Subculturing was performed using 0.05 % trypsin-EDTA solution (ThermoFisher, Cat. No. 15400054). The human adrenocortical cell line H295R (female) was obtained from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures and were used for experiments for a maximum passage of 12. DMEM/F-12 with HEPES medium supplemented with 2.5 % NU-serum (Corning, REF no. 3555000, 1 % ITS (Corning, REF no. 354352) and 1 % P/S was used for the H295R cells.

2.2. Cell seeding

96-well plates (Sarstedt) were washed with 70 % ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 64-17-5) before use. The cell density was 1.0*10⁴ cells/well for AR-ecoscreen cells and 2.0*10⁴ cells/well for VM7 cells (100 µL per well). H295R cells were added in 12 well plates (Sarstedt) with a cell density of 3.0*10⁵ cells/well (1500 µL per well). All plates were incubated for 24 h (37 °C, 5 % CO₂) before exposure.

For cellular imaging, the cell suspension of the VM7 and AR-ecoscreen cells, was the same concentration and volume as described before, but for the H295R cells the concentration was adjusted for 96 well plate: 2.79*10⁴ cells/well (100 µL per well). All cell suspensions were placed in a 96 well phenoplate from PerkinElmer (Part no. 6005430).

2.3. Preparation of exposures

All PS-MNPs were obtained from the Institute for Risk Assessment Sciences (IRAS, University of Utrecht, The Netherlands). The PS-MNPs were originally obtained from polysciences (more information in Table S1), after this IRAS suspended the PS-MNPs in ultra-purified water (UPW, obtained from Biosolve, water was filtered through 0.1 µm ULC/MS grade) in different concentrations: 10, 1, 0.1 and 0.01 mg/mL. For the preparation of exposure media, assay medium was used for VM7 and AR-ecoscreen cells, while for H295R cells growth medium was used. Exposures medium was prepared in assay medium, with end concentrations of 100, 10, 1, 0.1 and 1 µg/mL. The vehicle treated control for the PS-MNPs was 1 % UPW.

2.3.1. Cellular imaging of PS-MNPs

All cell types were plated out as described under 'cell seeding'. After 24 h, the cells were exposed to all sizes Fluorescent (F)-PS-MNPs (1 and 10 µg/mL) for 24 h (VM7/AR-ecoscreen cells) or 48 h (H295R cells). After the exposure time, the cells were washed 3 times with fresh assay medium. Hoechst 33258, pentahydrate (bis-benzimidide) was obtained from Invitrogen (Cat. no. H3570), an end concentration of 1 µg/mL was added to each well to show the nuclei of the cells. The cells were incubated for 5 min, following 2× washes with fresh assay medium. Images

were captured using the High content Imager (Operetta, Perkin Elmer) with the 63× water objective in confocal modus. The channel Alexa 488 was used to visualize the plastic particles, the Hoechst channel to image the nucleus, and the brightfield channel to image the cells. For the 3D imaging of the plastic particles and the nuclei, a Z-stack of 250 planes were imaged with a in between distance of 0.1 µm. The Harmony software version 4.9 (Perkin Elmer) was used to analyse the fluorescence intensity of the different channels for each plane of each well, but also to obtain the 3D images. The fluorescence intensities of the nuclei and plastic particles was drawn in a plot by using the software Graphpad prism 8.1.

2.3.2. Reporter gene assay

Besides the MNP solutions that were prepared for both cell lines in the reporter gene assay, other stock solutions were prepared. All compounds were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, unless stated otherwise. For the VM7 cells, a calibration curve of Estradiol (E2, Cat. No. 50-28-2) and ICI182780 (ICI, CAS No. 129453-61-8) was prepared in DMSO (0.5 % DMSO end concentration, obtained from Across organics, CAS no. 67-68-5) for agonism and antagonism, respectively. This was also done for the AR-ecoscreen cells with DHT (agonism, Cat. No. 521186) and Flutamide (antagonism, CAS. No. 13311-84-7). For the antagonistic assay, to each well containing ICI or DHT, an end concentration of 5 pM E2 or 60 pM DHT was added respectively. The negative control for all these conditions was 0.5 % DMSO. The well plates were incubated for 24 h. Afterwards, exposure medium was removed and 50 µL lysis buffer (details described in Table S2) was added into each well. The plate was measured in a Varioskan flash plate reader (ThermoFisher), the protocol was as follows: 100 µL glowmix (details described in Table S3) was added into one well and this well was measured. Then 100 µL brilliant black (50 mg/mL, Cas no. 2519-30-4) is added into the same well. This was repeated for each well. The output of the raw data gave relative light units (RLUs). From the raw data of agonism, percentages were calculated based on the highest concentration of E2 and DHT. For antagonism, the percentages were calculated based on the highest concentration of ICI and flutamide. Data analysis was performed in Graphpad prism 8.1, the calibration curves of E2, DHT, ICI and Flutamide were prepared by using nonlinear regression ($Y = A + (D-A)/(1 + (x/EC50)^{hill\text{slope}})$).

2.3.3. H295R steroidogenesis assay

Growth medium was removed from the wells with a vacuum pump and 1,5 mL of the exposure medium was added into the wells. The well plates were incubated for 48 h. Medium was collected and stored at -80 °C until use. Cells were used to perform an MTT assay.

2.4. MTT assay

After exposure, 750 µL for the H295R cells and 100 µL for VM7/AR-ecoscreen cells of the MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL in assay medium) was added into each well and incubated for 1 h in the incubator (37 °C, 5 % CO₂). Afterwards, the plates were centrifuged for 5 min, 2000 rpm at 20 °C. Supernatant was removed by a vacuum pump and 750 µL DMSO for H295R cells and 100 µL DMSO for VM7/AR-ecoscreen cells was added in each well. The plate was shaken for 5 min, 700 rpm at room temperature and the plate was measured in the Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (Biotek, Vermont USA) at 595 nm. Data analysis was performed in Excel and Graphpad prism 8.1. The average absorbance value of each experiment was calculated, and the average of three individual experiments was calculated. The vehicle control treated cells (1 % UPW) were stated at 100 %, and the averages of the different conditions were compared to the vehicle control treated cells. A student's t-test (unpaired t-test, two-tailed with CI 95 %) was performed to test significance. Concentrations were considered cytotoxic when cell viability was <80 % and > 120 %.

Fig. 2. Cell viability in ER, AR and H295R cells upon exposure to various sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs. (A) ER and (B) AR cells were exposed for 24 h and (C) H295R cells were exposed for 48 h to different concentrations and sizes of PS-MNPs. All bars represent the means \pm SD of three individual experiments ($N = 3$) performed in triplicate compared to the vehicle treated control cells (100 %). Dashed lines indicate 80 % and 120 % viability compared to vehicle-treated control. * Statistically significantly different from vehicle-treated control cells (* $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$).

2.5. LDH leakage

Two buffers; K_2HPO_4 and H_2K_4P were added together until a pH of 7.5. In this buffer, NADH (0.26 mM) and Na-Pyruvate (0.76 mM) were added. From the exposure medium, 50 μ L of each condition was added into a new 96-well plate, including the exposure medium of cells exposed to 100 % lysis buffer. 200 μ L of the prepared solution with NADH and Na-pyruvate was added in each well. A kinetic measurement using the Varioskan plater reader (340 nm) was used to determine the decrease in NADH in 5 min. Data analysis was performed with Excel and Graphpad prism 8.1. The average of the vehicle control treated cells (1 % UPW) were stated at 100 %, other conditions were compared with this control. Significance was determined using a student's t-test (unpaired t-test, two-tailed with CI 95 %). Any significant increase in LDH leakage cells is seen as cytotoxicity.

2.6. LC-MS/MS

H295R cells were seeded as described under 'cell seeding'. The H295R cells were exposed for 48 h to 50, 200, 1000 and 10,000 nm PS-MNPs at concentrations of 0.01–100 μ g/mL. The LCMS/MS method used for the quantitative analysis of steroid hormones, was the same as described before (Asimaki et al., 2022; Evangelista et al., 2024). In short, steroid hormones were extracted from 100 μ L exposure medium of H295R with solid phase extraction using 30 mg Plexa cartridges (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara California). Several native and isotopically labelled internal standards (Table S4) were used, 12 calibration points were used for underivatized steroid hormone analysis, while for the derivatized steroid hormone analysis 6 calibration points were used. Utilizing a SCIEX Triple Quad 6500+ System, a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer with an electrospray ionization source, the instrument operated in both positive and negative modes (SCIEX, Framingham, MA, USA). The optimized instrument parameters included a curtain gas set at

35 psi, temperature at 600 $^{\circ}$ C, ion source gas 1 at 70 psi, ion source gas 2 at 50 psi, and ion spray voltage ranging from 5500 to -4500 V. Steroid hormones were separated using a Kinetex[®] C18 LC Column (2.6 μ m, 100 \times 2.1 mm) obtained from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). The column was maintained at 40 $^{\circ}$ C and employed on an ExionLC system (SCIEX, Framingham, MA, U.S.) featuring a binary pump and auto-sampler. For the underivatized LCMS/MS method settings were as follows: A: 0.2 mM NH_4F in MiliQ and B: MeOH, with changing ratio with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. One run was 22 min, where the analytes were monitored by multiple reaction monitoring. Steroid hormones that were not detected in exposure medium were 5 α -THDOC, etioch-3 α -one, 5 α -androsterone, 5 α -androstenediol, 17 α -hydroxydihydroprogesterone, and aldosterone. With the derivatized LCMS/MS method, estrone (E1), 17- β -estradiol (17 β E2) and estriol (E3) were measured. To prepare the dansylation of the samples 1 mg/mL dansyl chloride (Sigma-Aldrich) and the carbonate buffer was added to each sample. Data analysis was performed by normalizing the data per experiment to the control (defined as 1). The effect of exposure to PS-MNPs on the hormone levels in H295R cells was expressed in fold changes in comparison with the control. The average and standard deviation of the average fold changes per experiment was calculated and a one-way ANOVA Dunnett's multiple comparisons test (compare the mean of each column with the mean of a control column) was applied to determine statistical significance.

2.7. Gene expression

H295R cells were seeded as described under 'cell seeding'. The H295R cells were exposed for 48 h to 50, 200, 1000 and 10,000 nm PS-MNPs at a concentration of 10 μ g/mL. The positive control that was included was an end concentration of 30 μ M forskolin (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 66575–29-9). RNA was extracted from H295R cells using chloroform extraction. H295R cells which were exposed to PS-MNPs were collected and placed on ice. The cells were washed with cold

Fig. 3. Internalization of FPS-MNPs in VM7 cells. Fig. A-D shows the 2D pictures of the nucleus (Hoechst, blue) and the FPS-MNPs (green). A brightfield picture was overlaid with the nuclei and FPS-MNPs (E-H). Several z-stacks were made to obtain 3D pictures of VM7 cells (I-L). In the graphs (M-P), the intensity of the fluorescent intensity of PS-MNPs and Hoechst was determined in each z-stack. More detailed pictures are shown in Fig. S1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

PBS, 500 μ L trizol (Molecular research center, inc. iTaq™, Cat no. TR-118) was then added in each well. The plates were then frozen at -80°C for 20 min. The cells were scraped off the plate and transferred into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf Tube. 100 μ L icecold chloroform (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 67–66-3) was added to each tube and vortexed for 20 s. This mixture was centrifuged for 12,000 g, 15 min on 4°C (same for every step). 200 μ L of the upper layer is transferred to a new Eppendorf tube. To this tube, 250 μ L ice cold isopropanol (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 67–63-0) was added and vortexed. The tubes were incubated for 1 h at 4°C . Supernatant was removed and 750 μ L ice cold ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 64–17-5) was added, and were vortexed. The tubes were centrifuged and the supernatant was again removed and the pallet washed with 750 μ L ice cold ethanol. Supernatant was removed and the pallet was dried for 10 min at room temperature. Afterwards, the pellet was resuspended in 15 μ L cold sterile water and kept on ice. RNA levels were measured with the Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (Biotek, Vermont USA) at 230 nm. RNA samples were normalized to 50 ng/ μ L, and cDNA was prepared in the cDNA-Biorad mycycler™ thermal cycler to prepare cDNA. The cDNA was diluted 10 times, and several genes were tested (Table S5 for a detailed primer list). RT-qPCR was performed in the Biorad CFX96™ real-time system and the protocol was as follows: 5 min at 95°C , followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C and 45 s at 60°C . The melt curve was 5 s at 60°C and increasing 0.5°C per step until 95°C . For data analysis, the baseline settings were adjusted to apply fluorescence drift correction and baseline subtracted curve fit. The graph was converted to a log scale and the baseline threshold was set at 600 relative fluorescent units (RFUs). Normalized gene expression ($\Delta\Delta\text{Cq}$) was calculated using the Biorad CFX Maestro Software (version 2.3, Bio-Rad Laboratories), using geometric means of three reference genes GAPDH, HRTPI and TBP for normalization (Vandesompele et al., 2002). Relative

expression of each gene was calculated in comparison with the control (1 % UPW) per experiment using MS-Excel. Genes that showed a Ct value of >32 were considered as not detected. Data from all three individual experiments were combined and means and SD were calculated. A student's *t*-test (unpaired *t*-test, two-tailed with CI 95 %) was performed to determine if the different conditions had a significance effect on gene expression in comparison with the control ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results

3.1. Cell viability

All cell lines were exposed to various sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs, and an MTT assay was performed. MTT reduction, an indicator of mitochondrial function, was used as marker for cell viability. The threshold for effect was set at an arbitrary $<80\%$ and $>120\%$. Only exposure to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of 1000 nm PS-MNPs exceeded those thresholds and caused an increased mitochondrial activity in the AR and H295R cell lines above the 120 %, as depicted in Fig. 2.

3.2. VM7 cells

3.2.1. Uptake of PS-MNPs in VM7 cells

Confocal microscopy was employed to evaluate the internalization of FPS-MNPs by VM7 cells after exposure to 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of these particles. The imaging results indicate that VM7 cells exhibited internalization of 50, 200 and 1000 nm FPS-MNPs (Fig. 3 and Fig. S1). Further examination through 3D imaging demonstrated that these particles were in close proximity to the cell nucleus.

The intensity of fluorescence emitted by the particles and the

Fig. 4. Estrogen receptor activity upon PS-MNP exposure in VM7 cells. (A) Agonistic and (B) antagonistic effects on estrogen receptor activity by various sizes and concentrations PS-MNPs. VM7 cells were exposed to different sizes (50–10,000 nm) and concentrations (0.01–100 µg/mL) of PS-MNPs. E2 was used as a positive control for ER activation, while ICI182780 (ICI) was used as positive control of ER inhibition. For the antagonistic assay, 5 pM E2 was added to each exposure. Results are shown as means with standard deviations of individual experiments ($N = 6$ for positive controls E2 and ICI, and $N = 3$ for PS-MNP treatment) performed in triplicate. The dotted lines represent the 95 % CI.

Hoechst-stained nuclei was quantified across Z-stacked images. This analysis indicates that 50, 200 and 1000 nm particles were located at the same height as the cell nuclei (Fig. 3M-P), confirming their proximity to the nucleus.

The number of particles internalized appeared size-dependent, with smaller sizes being more internalized than larger sizes.

3.2.2. Estrogen receptor activity

VM7 cells were exposed to various sizes (50–10,000 nm) and concentrations (0.01–100 µg/mL) of PS-MNPs for 24 h to determine the effects on ER activity. E2 was used as a positive control for ER activation and had an apparent EC₅₀ of 0.0011 µg/mL (3.9 pM). None of the sizes or concentrations of PS-MNPs displayed an agonistic effect on the ER (Fig. 4A). Next, the ER antagonistic effects of the same sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs were tested in combination with 5 pM E2 (Fig. 4B). The known ER antagonist ICI182780 (ICI) was used as positive control for inhibition of ER activation and displayed an EC₅₀ of 0.14 µg/mL (226 pM). E2-induced ER activation was not inhibited by any of the test conditions with PS-MNPs (Fig. 4B).

3.3. AR-ecscreen cells

3.3.1. Uptake of PS-MNPs in AR-ecscreen cells

To determine uptake of particles by AR-ecscreen cells, cells were exposed to 1 µg/mL FPS-MNPs, and analyzed by confocal microscopy. Microscopic analysis revealed the internalization of 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs by the AR-ecscreen cells (Fig. 5 and Fig. S2). Specifically, 50 nm

particles were found in close proximity to the cell nucleus. This observation was further confirmed by the intensity graphs, which showed that both fluorescent and DAPI signals were most intense at the same height (Fig. 5M).

3.3.2. Androgen receptor activity

To determine the effects of PS-MNPs on AR activity, AR-ecscreen cells were exposed to different sizes (50–10,000 nm) and concentrations (0.01–100 µg/mL) PS-MNPs for 24 h. DHT was used as positive control for AR activation and had an EC₅₀ value of 0.02 µg/mL (62.9 pM) (Fig. 6A). None of the PS-MNPs sizes or concentrations tested statistically significantly induced AR activation. To determine whether PS-MNPs were able to antagonize AR activation, cells were co-exposed to 60 pM DHT and PS-MNPs. Flutamide was used as a positive control for AR inhibition and displayed an EC₅₀ value of 255 µg/mL (923 nM) (Fig. 6B). The results showed that none of the PS-MNPs sizes or concentrations statistically significantly inhibited DHT-induced AR activation.

3.4. H295R steroidogenesis

3.4.1. Uptake of PS-MNPs in the H295R cell line

Confocal microscopy analysis was used to determine whether FPS-MNPs (1 µg/mL) were taken up by H295R cells (Fig. 7 and Fig. S3). The analysis of fluorescent signals showed that the 50, 200 and 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were found at the same height as the nuclei, demonstrating internalization within the cells rather than surface adhesion. Moreover,

Fig. 5. Internalization of FPS-MNPs in the AR-ecoscreen cells. Fig. A-D shows the 2D pictures of the nucleus (Hoechst, blue) and the FPS-MNPs (green). A brightfield picture was overlaid with the nuclei and FPS-MNPs (E-H). Several z-stacks were made to obtain 3D pictures of AR-ecoscreen cells (I-L). In the graphs (M-P), the intensity of the fluorescent intensity of PS-MNPs and Hoechst was determined in each z-stack. More detailed pictures are shown in Fig. S2. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

these particles were localized around the nucleus. The 10,000 nm FPS particles were not taken up by the H295R cells (Fig. 7D, H, L, P).

3.4.2. LDH leakage

Given the substantial internalization of PS-MNPs by H295R cells, a LDH leakage assay was conducted to further assess cellular integrity. Exposure of cells to the various sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs did not result in higher LDH leakage compared to the vehicle control treated cells (Fig. 8). Rather, a statistically significant decrease in LDH leakage was observed with exposure to 10,000 nm PS-MNPs (1 and 10 µg/mL) and 1000 nm PS-MNPs (0.1 µg/mL).

3.4.3. Steroidogenesis

To assess the impact of PS-MNPs on the biosynthesis of steroid hormones, H295R cells were exposed to various sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs for 48 h. Next, 17 steroid hormones were measured in the exposure media using LC-MS/MS. Generally, most statistically significant effects on steroidogenesis were seen with 50 and 200 nm sized particles (Fig. 9 and Fig. S4). However, these effects did not show clear and consistent concentration-dependent trends. There was no statistically significant effect on the corticosteroid levels in media of PS-MNPs exposed H295R cells compared to media of vehicle-treated control cells. There was a statistically significant increase in progesterone levels in media after exposure of H295R cells to 100 µg/mL 50 nm PS-MNPs (Fig. 9A). In addition, 17 α -OH-progesterone levels were statistically significantly increased in media after exposure of H295R cells to 1 µg/mL 10,000 nm (Fig. 9D) and 10 µg/mL 200 nm and 1000 nm particles (Fig. 9B and C). For the androgens, only exposure to 10 µg/mL 200 nm PS-MNPs resulted in a statistically significant increase in DHT levels in the H295R culture media. Estrone and estradiol levels were unaffected in media of H295R cells exposed to PS-MNPs at all sizes and concentrations tested. Interestingly, estriol (E3) levels were decreased 25–37.5

% by various concentrations of 50 and 1000 nm PS-MNPs compared to vehicle-treated controls, though no apparent concentration-dependency was observed (Fig. 9A and C).

3.4.4. Gene expression

In H295R cells, the effects of different sizes PS-MNPs (10 µg/mL) on gene expression of selected steroidogenic enzymes, oxidative stress markers and functional markers were assessed by qPCR. Forskolin (30 µM) served as a positive control for induction of gene expression. There was no statistically significant effect of PS-MNPs on the gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes tested (Fig. 10A-D). Expression of steroidogenic enzymes CYP3A4 and 17B1-HSD either approached or exceeded the designated cut-off Ct value of 32 (Fig. S5), and could therefore not reliably be assessed. Exposure of H295R cells to 50 nm PS-MNPs statistically significantly increased gene expression of two oxidative stress markers, GPX and SOD1, by 1.30- and 1.23-fold, respectively (Fig. 10F and G). The expression of ATM and SOD2 was unaffected by PS-MNP exposure (Fig. 10E and H). None of the cellular markers tested, *i.e.* GJA1 and Pannexin, were statistically significantly affected by PS-MNPs (Fig. 10I-J). Nevertheless, for all genes tested, expression appeared to be slightly, albeit non-statistically significantly, increased after exposure to 50 nm PS-MNPs.

4. Discussion and conclusion

In this study, endocrine disrupting properties of PS-MNPs were screened for the first time using established *in vitro* tests in regulatory chemical safety assessment. We show that PS-MNPs did not activate nor inhibit estrogen and androgen receptor activity *in vitro*, in sizes ranging from 50 to 10,000 nm and concentrations ranging between 0.01 µg/mL and 100 µg/mL. This may partly be due to the limited internalization of the particles in these cells. H295R cells showed more uptake of PS-MNPs

Fig. 6. Androgen receptor activity upon PS-MNPs exposure in AR-ecoscreen cells. (A) agonistic and (B) antagonistic effects on androgen receptor activity by various sizes and concentrations PS-MNPs. The AR-ecoscreen GR KO cells were exposed to different sizes (50–10,000 nm) and concentrations (0.01–100 µg/mL). For the agonistic assay, DHT was used as a positive control, while for the antagonistic assay flutamide was used. To determine the AR antagonistic effects, cells were co-exposed to DHT (60 pM) and PS-MNPs. Results are shown as means with standard deviations of individual experiments ($N = 6$ for controls DHT and Flutamide, $N = 3$ for PS-MNPs treatment) performed in triplicate. The dotted lines represent the 95 % CI.

and some statically significant changes in some hormone levels were observed. However, the effects were not apparently size- and concentration dependent.

4.1. Uptake of particles

Our study showed that PS-MNPs were taken up by the ER and AR reporter cells and the H295R cells, albeit with marked differences. While VM7 cells and H295R internalized particles up to 1000 nm, AR-ecoscreen cells internalized only particles up to 200 nm. In addition, more particles were detected in H295R cells than in AR-ecoscreen, and VM7 cells. Partly, this may be explained by different exposure times to FPS-MNPs, *i.e.* 48 h for H295R and, 24 h for AR-ecoscreen and VM7 cells. However, the differences in the FPS-MNPs internalization between AR-ecoscreen and VM7 cells suggest that cell-type specific differences in uptake mechanisms may also play a role. The main uptake mechanism of MNPs is believed to be endocytosis (Firdessa et al., 2014; Lesniak et al., 2013; Rejman et al., 2004). While all cell lines in this study are capable of performing endocytosis, it is important to note that each endocytotic pathway has a maximum size limit for nanoparticles to be internalized (Kinnear et al., 2017). In addition, VM7 cells and H295R cells are derived from a human breast cancer patient and an adrenal cancer patient, respectively, while AR-ecoscreen cells originate from hamster ovaries. A distinctive feature of cancer cells is macropinocytosis, whereas most non-cancerous cells are non-macropinocytotic (Cong et al., 2021). This distinction might explain why VM7 cells and H295R cells were able to uptake 1000 nm FPS-MNPs, while AR-ecoscreen cells

did not. Furthermore, apart from the difference in cancerous *versus* non-cancerous cell type, it should be taken into consideration that AR-ecoscreen cells originate from hamster, while VM7 cells and H295R cells are of human origin, which could also influence the uptake process of MNPs. Moreover, the uptake of MNPs might be influenced by corona formation around the PS-MNPs, which varies depending on proteins, lipids, phospholipids and carbohydrates present in the different media (Lesniak et al., 2013). It is suggested that PS-MNPs covered with a protein corona adhere to the cell membrane and may interact with lipids and protein, potentially triggering energy-dependent pathways such as endocytosis. Interestingly, a difference in intracellular localization of the FPS-MNPs was noticed in the three cell types. To our knowledge, only one study described that 100 nm FPS-MNPs were discovered around the nuclei in small intestine cells (IPEC-J2 cells) (Binder et al., 2023). Other studies describe that PS-MNPs were taken up, but the localization of the PS-MNPs is not identify (Dusza et al., 2022; Firdessa et al., 2014; Ruan et al., 2023) or is considered cytoplasmic (Banerjee et al., 2021). Therefore, more studies are needed to elucidate the intracellular localization of MNPs. This could be performed by tracking the internalization of fluorescent MNPs with a confocal microscope.

In addition to the differential internalization of FPS-MNPs among the three cell types employed, our study shows some effects on cell viability and membrane integrity. At the highest concentration tested (100 µg/mL) with 1000 nm particles, an increased MTT reduction above the arbitrary 120 % threshold was observed in AR and H295R cells, but not in VM7 cells. MTT reduction is a marker of mitochondrial activity, which is typically used as marker for cell viability. However, it is known

Fig. 7. The internalization of FPS-MNPs in the H295R cells. Fig. A-D shows the 2D pictures of the nucleus (Hoechst, blue) and the FPS-MNPs (green). A brightfield picture was overlaid with the nuclei and FPS-MNPs (E-H). Several z-stacks were made to obtain 3D pictures of H295R cells (I-L). In the graphs (M-P), the intensity of the fluorescent intensity of PS-MNPs and Hoechst was determined in each z-stack. More detailed pictures are shown in Fig. S3. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Membrane integrity of H295R cells after exposure to PS-MNPs. LDH leakage was determined of H295R cells which were exposed for 48 h to different sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs. The bars represent the means of three individual experiments performed in triplicate \pm SD compared to the vehicle control treated cells (1 % UPW). Lysis buffer was used as positive control. The dotted lines are set at $y = 80$ % and 120 %.

that several processes such as oxidative stress can impact MTT readouts (Stepanenko and Dmitrenko, 2015). Additional studies with H295R cells, which showed the highest uptake of particles, indicated some statistically significant decreases in LDH leakage upon exposure to 1000 and 10,000 nm particles, suggesting increased cell membrane integrity. Considering the low uptake of larger particles, our results suggest that the effects on mitochondrial activity and cell membrane integrity are not due to intracellular effects of the particles. Studies with other cell types typically show increase LDH leakage at high concentrations 10–1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 50–1000 nm PS-MNPs (Dusza et al., 2022; Saenen et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022), which may also occur due to oxidative stress, as the

integrity of the membrane can be compromised due to lipid peroxidation (Jovanović et al., 2010).

Previous studies show conflicting results regarding the impact of PS-MNPs on oxidative stress. One study showed that exposure to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 2000 nm PS-MNPs caused increased oxidative stress in skin cells (Schmidt et al., 2023). However, another study showed that a 24 h exposure to 1–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 50–100 nm PS-MNPs did not cause oxidative stress in Caco-2/HT29 monolayers (Domenech et al., 2020). In the present study, a potential effect on oxidative stress was investigated by studying gene expression of several well-known oxidative stress markers and cellular markers in H295R cells. Gene expression of cellular markers

Fig. 9. The effect of PS-MNPs on steroid hormone levels in H295R cells. Heatmaps showing changes in steroid hormone levels in H295R culture media upon exposure to various concentrations of PS-MNPs, with various sizes (A) 50 nm, (B) 200 nm, (C) 1000 nm and (D) 10,000 nm. The numbers written in each cell represents the average absolute hormone concentration in pg/mL ($N = 3$, in triplicate). The colour of each cell represents the fold change ranging from 0.5 (green) to 1.5 (purple), control = 1. The fold-changes are the average changes calculated based on three individual experiments ($N = 3$) in triplicate. Statistical significance was calculated with one-way ANOVA, Dunnett's multiple comparisons test (* $p < 0.05$). More detailed information about the fold-changes is shown in Fig. S4. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

was not affected by different sizes PS-MNPs at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. However, gene expression of oxidative stress markers SOD1 and GPX1 was statistically significantly increased, but only after exposure to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 50 nm PS-MNPs. SOD1 is an enzyme that converts $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$ to H_2O_2 and protects all cellular structures except the mitochondrial matrix (Che et al., 2016). On the other hand, GPX1 is an intracellular antioxidant enzyme that catalyzes the conversion of H_2O_2 into H_2O to counteract its harmful effects (Lubos et al., 2011). GPX1 is also involved in growth factor-mediated signal transduction, maintenance of normal thiol redox-balance and mitochondrial function. Our study showed that exposure to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 50 nm PS-MNPs caused an increase in SOD1 and GPX1 gene expression, while exposure to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 1000 nm PS-MNPs resulted in increased mitochondrial activity in H295R cells. Similar to our results, another study also described increased mitochondrial activity and increased GPX1 and SOD1 gene expression in Caco-2 cells after exposure to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 2000 nm PS-MNPs (Saenen et al., 2023). This suggests that alterations in SOD1 and GPX1 gene expression and changes in mitochondrial activity may be correlated and indicate slight oxidative stress of H295R cells in the present study.

The fact that small MNPs have the capacity to enter human cells raises concerns regarding their potential to disturb physiological processes. Exposure to MNP is associated with several health effects, such as immune responses, neurotoxicity, reproductive and developmental toxicity (Y. Li et al., 2023). However, little information is available

about the mechanisms underlying the potential health effects caused by MNPs. Given the many studies linking plastic additives to endocrine disruption, and studies showing cellular uptake of MNPs, it is pertinent to investigate the potential endocrine disrupting effects of MNPs. While existing studies primarily detect bisphenols and phthalates leaching from MNPs.

(X. L. Cao and Corriveau, 2008; Y. Cao et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2019; Hirai et al., 2011; C. Li et al., 2022; Paluselli et al., 2019; Schrank et al., 2019), there is limited data on the full spectrum of plastic additives that may leach out, potentially posing additional risks. Future research should aim to quantify the levels of plastic additives that possibly leach from MNPs and their contribution to the body burden of these compounds. However, this may be complicated by the diversity of additives used for the various plastics, by the level of weathering (older MNPs may contain less additives than those that have not been exposed to environmental factors), and perhaps also the formation of a layer of biomolecules on the MNPs in the organism that may restrict leaching of additives from the particles. In European regulatory assessment of endocrine modalities, the next step after computational modelling includes *in vitro* screening of androgen and estrogen receptor trans-activation and interaction with steroidogenesis.

Steroidogenic enzymes

Oxidative stress markers

Functional markers

Fig. 10. The effect of PS-MNPs on gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes, oxidative stress and functional markers. H295R cells were exposed for 48 h to 10 µg/mL PS-MNPs in different sizes: 50, 200, 1000 and 10,000 nm. The vehicle treated cells were exposed to 1 % UPW and forskolin (30 µM) was used as positive control. Gene expression was normalized to three housekeeping genes (GAPDH, TBP and HPRT1). Bars represent the average ± SD fold change of three individual experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical significance was determined by a student's t -test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.00001$). Abbreviations: ATM, ataxia-telangiectasia mutated; CYP, cytochrome P450; GJA1, connexin 43; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; SOD, superoxide dismutase; 3β-HSD, 3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase.

4.2. Endocrine mode of action

4.2.1. Estrogen and androgen receptor activation

In this study, PS-MNPs had no agonistic or antagonistic effects on ER and AR activity in our reporter gene assays. To our knowledge, there are no other *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies describing the effect of PS-MNPs on ER and AR activity, specifically. A study examined ER activation of leachate from MNPs detected in the digestive tract of murre using a reporter gene assay consisting of HEK293 cells transfected with human estrogen receptor 1 and 3xERE luciferase reporter plasmids (Michishita et al., 2023). ERα activation was observed in three out of the nine leachate samples with a response of 27 %, 32 % and 31 % of the maximal E2 activation. Though, it is important to note that leachate from MNPs likely contains plastic additives that are known to interact with the ER (Benjamin et al., 2017; Fenichel et al., 2013; Frenzilli et al., 2021; Meeker and Ferguson, 2014). Taken together, there are no indications of

a direct effect of PS-MNPs on ER and AR activity *in vitro*.

4.2.2. Steroidogenesis

The H295R steroidogenesis assay is the gold standard to investigate the impact of chemicals on steroidogenesis. To our knowledge, this is the first study to explore the effects of PS-MNPs in this assay. In the OECD test guideline of the H295R steroidogenesis assay (TG456), a substance is considered to affect steroidogenesis when there is a statistically significant change in E2 or T levels of <0.667 or > 1.5-fold for two consecutive test concentrations, compared to vehicle-treated controls (OECD, 2023). In our study, exposure to PS-MNPs did not statistically significantly affect T and E2 levels in culture media of H295R cells, which would lead to conclude that PS-MNPs do not affect steroidogenesis. However, several experimental animal studies suggest that repeated exposure to PS-MNPs can affect circulating steroid hormone levels *in vivo*. For example, six-week-old male mice, when given 10 mg/

mL of 50, 4000, and 10,000 nm PS-MNPs orally every day for a period of 28 days, exhibited a small but significant reduction in serum T levels (Jin et al., 2021). The highest reduction (0.5 fold) was seen after exposure to 10,000 nm PS-MNPs. Another study showed a decrease of $\pm 60\%$ in serum E2 levels in adult female rats when given orally 0.1 mg/day 5000 nm PS-MNPs for a period of 24–26 days (Haddadi et al., 2022). PS-MNPs were detected in the testes of male mice (Jin et al., 2021) and in the duodenum and ovarian tissues of female rats (Haddadi et al., 2022). It is impossible to compare our *in vitro* concentrations to the *in vivo* concentrations, since the specific MNP concentrations in these tissues were not determined. Despite the lack of effects on E2 and T, when considering a broader profile of 17 steroid hormones in our H295R assay, a statistically significant decrease in E3 levels was observed upon exposure to 50 nm PS-MNPs (0.01, 1, 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and 1000 nm (1 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) PS-MNPs. E3 is formed through 16-alpha hydroxylation of E1 or E2 by cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4), mainly in the liver and at high levels by the placenta during pregnancy (Lee et al., 2003; Robinson and Klein, 2012; Tsuchiya et al., 2005; Tulchinsky et al., 1972). In our H295R cells, CYP3A4 was not expressed at high enough levels to determine the effects of PS-MNPs on gene expression of this enzyme. Still, the potential effects of PS-MNPs on E3 formation warrants further studies given the association with placental health and pregnancy outcomes. These studies should then be performed in relevant placental models and focus on internalization of particles as well as functional endpoints (Dusza et al., 2023).

4.3. Relevance/Risk assessment

Toxicological risk assessment of MNPs is challenging and still in its infancy. While mounting evidence shows the wide-spread presence of MNPs in humans, adequate risk assessment is hampered by the lack of good toxicological data. Exposure assessment is challenged by the variety of MNP detection methods among studies. A study that measured plastic polymer concentration in blood of 20 human volunteers using FITC-GC/MS revealed an average concentration of 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, with the highest measured PS concentration being 4.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Leslie et al., 2022). These concentrations are in the low range of the PS concentrations tested in our *in vitro* study (0.01–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). However, while the study with human volunteers showed the presence of PS polymers in blood, the method did not allow to calculate the number of particles that was present. This clearly hampers a good comparison of human and experimental animal studies with mechanistic *in vitro* studies. In our study, we chose to normalize exposure based on concentrations of PS-MNPs rather than calculate exposure based on a specific number of particles. This approach resulted in varying number of particles for each size, with more particles for 50 nm and fewer particles of 10,000 nm at the same concentration. Still, it was clear that the smaller PS particles more readily entered the cells in the present study. Therefore, the effects on mitochondrial activity and cell membrane integrity in this study were most likely caused by extracellularly present MNPs. Though, as described above, the occurrence of mild oxidative stress cannot be excluded. The effects on steroidogenesis by smaller MNPs are most likely attributed to intracellular, biochemical events. This stresses the necessity to account for size and number of particles, as well as the potential of the particles to enter a specific cell type in toxicological studies. Moreover, to reflect a more human-relevant exposure scenario, toxicological assessment should consider potential effects of (mixtures of) other polymers besides PS, since these can also be detected in human samples, such as blood (Leslie et al., 2022). Lastly, *in vitro* exposure scenarios typically comprise short exposure times due to experimental limitations, such as confluency of cell layers and exhaustion of culture media. While in reality, humans face chronic daily exposure to MNPs, potentially leading to MNP accumulation in various organs (Kannan and Vimalkumar, 2021). Therefore, further studies into prolonged exposure will be essential for a comprehensive assessment of potential effects aligning with human experiences.

Overall, this study contributes to the knowledge base regarding the potential toxicological effects of PS-MNPs. Our study shows that the internalization of PS-MNPs differs with particle size and among cell lines. This should be considered in future toxicological studies and may help discern between intra- and extracellular events. Exposure to PS-MNPs did not affect estrogen or androgen receptor (ant)agonism in standardized ER and AR reporter gene assays. However, statistically significant effects were found in the H295R steroidogenesis assay, though particularly on E3 levels. While there was no clear concentration- or size-dependency, the importance of E3 in the placenta warrants further studies in the potential effects of MNPs during pregnancy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jeske van Boxel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Rani R.J. Khargi:** Investigation. **Sandra M. Nijmeijer:** Investigation. **Manuel T. Heinzelmann:** Methodology, Investigation. **Daniel Da Costa Pereira:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Marja H. Lamoree:** Supervision. **Majorie B.M. van Duursen:** Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Peter Cenijn, Maxim Carlier and Jacco Koekoek for their help during this research. This research was supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under AURORA grant agreement No 964827.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2024.105938>.

References

- Akingbemi, B.T., Sottas, C.M., Koulova, A.I., Klinefelter, G.R., Hardy, M.P., 2004. Inhibition of testicular steroidogenesis by the xenoestrogen bisphenol A is associated with reduced pituitary luteinizing hormone secretion and decreased steroidogenic enzyme gene expression in rat Leydig cells. *Endocrinology* 145 (2), 592–603. <https://doi.org/10.1210/EN.2003-1174>.
- Asimaki, K., Vazakidou, P., van Tol, H.T.A., Oei, C.H.Y., Modder, E.A., van Duursen, M.B.M., Gadella, B.M., 2022. Bovine *in vitro* oocyte maturation and embryo production used as a model for testing endocrine disrupting chemicals eliciting female reproductive toxicity with diethylstilbestrol as a showcase compound. *Front. Toxicol.* 4, 811285. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FTOX.2022.811285/FULL>.
- Aurisano, N., Huang, L., Milà i Canals, L., Jolliet, O., Fantke, P., 2021. Chemicals of concern in plastic toys. *Environ. Int.* 146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106194>.
- Aves, A.R., Revell, L.E., Gaw, S., Ruffell, H., Schuddeboom, A., Wotherspoon, N.E., Larue, M., McDonald, A.J., 2022. First evidence of microplastics in Antarctic snow. *Cryosphere* 16 (6), 2127–2145. <https://doi.org/10.5194/TC-16-2127-2022>.
- Banerjee, A., Billey, L.O., Shelver, W.L., 2021. Uptake and toxicity of polystyrene micro/nanoplastics in gastric cells: effects of particle size and surface functionalization. *PLoS One* 16 (12). <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0260803>.
- Bashir, S.M., Kimiko, S., Mak, C.W., Fang, J.K.H., Gonçalves, D., 2021. Personal care and cosmetic products as a potential source of environmental contamination by microplastics in a densely populated Asian City. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 604. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMARS.2021.683482/BIBTEX>.
- Benjamin, S., Masai, E., Kamimura, N., Takahashi, K., Anderson, R.C., Faisal, P.A., 2017. Phthalates impact human health: epidemiological evidences and plausible

- mechanism of action. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 340, 360–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2017.06.036>.
- Binder, A.R.D., Mussack, V., Kirchner, B., Pfaffl, M.W., 2023. Uptake and effects of polystyrene nanoparticles in comparison to non-plastic silica nanoparticles on small intestine cells (IPEC-J2). *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 262, 115147 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOENV.2023.115147>.
- Braun, T., Ehrlich, L., Henrich, W., Koepfel, S., Lomako, I., Schwabl, P., Liebmann, B., 2021. Detection of microplastic in human placenta and meconium in a clinical setting. *Pharmaceutics* 13 (7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/PHARMACEUTICS13070921>.
- Brown, D.M., Wilson, M.R., MacNee, W., Stone, V., Donaldson, K., 2001. Size-dependent proinflammatory effects of ultrafine polystyrene particles: a role for surface area and oxidative stress in the enhanced activity of ultrafines. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 175 (3), 191–199. <https://doi.org/10.1006/TAAP.2001.9240>.
- Campen, M., Nihart, A., Garcia, M., Liu, R., Olewine, M., Castillo, E., Bleske, B., Scott, J., Howard, T., Gonzalez-Estrella, J., Adolph, N., Gallego, D., Hayek, E.El., 2024. Bioaccumulation of microplastics in decedent human brains assessed by pyrolysis gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Res. Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/RS.3.RS-4345687/V1>.
- Cao, X.L., Corrievau, J., 2008. Migration of bisphenol A from polycarbonate baby and water bottles into water under severe conditions. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 56 (15), 6378–6381. <https://doi.org/10.1021/JF800870B>.
- Cao, Y., Lin, H., Zhang, K., Xu, S., Yan, M., Leung, K.M.Y., Lam, P.K.S., 2022. Microplastics: a major source of phthalate esters in aquatic environments. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 432, 128731 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2022.128731>.
- Chang, W.H., Tsai, Y.S., Wang, J.Y., Chen, H.L., Yang, W.H., Lee, C.C., 2019. Sex hormones and oxidative stress mediated phthalate-induced effects in prostatic enlargement. *Environ. Int.* 126, 184–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVIINT.2019.02.006>.
- Chatuphonprasert, W., Jarukamjorn, K., Ellinger, I., 2018. Physiology and pathophysiology of steroid biosynthesis, transport and metabolism in the human placenta. *Front. Pharmacol.* 9 (SEP) <https://doi.org/10.3389/FPHAR.2018.01027>.
- Che, M., Wang, R., Li, X., Wang, H.Y., Zheng, X.F.S., 2016. Expanding roles of superoxide dismutases in cell regulation and cancer. *Drug Discov. Today* 21 (1), 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DRUDIS.2015.10.001>.
- Chen, Q., Allgeier, A., Yin, D., Hollert, H., 2019. Leaching of endocrine disrupting chemicals from marine microplastics and mesoplastics under common life stress conditions. *Environ. Int.* 130, 104938 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVIINT.2019.104938>.
- Codrington, J., Varnum, A.A., Hildebrandt, L., Pröfrock, D., Bidhan, J., Khodamoradi, K., Höhme, A.L., Held, M., Evans, A., Velasquez, D., Yarrowborough, C.C., Ghane-Motlagh, B., Agarwal, A., Achua, J., Pozzi, E., Mesquita, F., Petrella, F., Miller, D., Ramasamy, R., 2024. Detection of microplastics in the human penis. *Int. J. Impot. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41443-024-00930-6>.
- Cong, V.T., Tilley, R.D., Sharbeen, G., Phillips, P.A., Gaus, K., Gooding, J.J., 2021. How to exploit different endocytosis pathways to allow selective delivery of anticancer drugs to cancer cells over healthy cells. *Chem. Sci.* 12 (46), 15407. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1SC04656J>.
- Dąbrowska, A., Mielanżczuk, M., Syczewski, M., 2022. The Raman spectroscopy and SEM/EDS investigation of the primary sources of microplastics from cosmetics available in Poland. *Chemosphere* 308, 136407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2022.136407>.
- Diaz-Basantes, M.F., Conesa, J.A., Fullana, A., 2020. Microplastics in honey, beer, milk and refreshments in Ecuador as emerging contaminants. *Sustainability* 12 (14), 5514. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12145514>.
- Domenech, J., Hernández, A., Rubio, L., Marcos, R., Cortés, C., 2020. Interactions of polystyrene nanoparticles with in vitro models of the human intestinal barrier. *Arch. Toxicol.* 94 (9), 2997–3012. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00204-020-02805-3/FIGURES/9>.
- Donkers, J.M., Höppener, E.M., Grigoriev, I., Will, L., Melgert, B.N., van der Zaan, B., van de Steeg, E., Kooter, I.M., 2022. Advanced epithelial lung and gut barrier models demonstrate passage of microplastic particles. *Micropl. Nanopl.* 2 (1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S43591-021-00024-W>.
- Dusza, H.M., Katrukha, E.A., Nijmeijer, S.M., Akhmanova, A., Vethaak, A.D., Walker, D. I., Legler, J., 2022. Uptake, transport, and toxicity of pristine and weathered micro- and nanoplastics in human placenta cells. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 130 (9) <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP10873>.
- Dusza, H.M., van Boxel, J., van Duursen, M.B.M., Forsberg, M.M., Legler, J., Vähäkangas, K.H., 2023. Experimental human placental models for studying uptake, transport and toxicity of micro- and nanoplastics. *Sci. Total Environ.* 860, 160403 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCIOTOTENV.2022.160403>.
- Eriksen, M., Mason, S., Wilson, S., Box, C., Zellers, A., Edwards, W., Farley, H., Amato, S., 2013. Microplastic pollution in the surface waters of the Laurentian Great Lakes. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 77 (1–2), 177–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2013.10.007>.
- Ernst, J., Grabiec, U., Falk, K., Dehghani, F., Schaedlich, K., 2020. The endocrine disruptor DEHP and the ECS: analysis of a possible crosstalk. *Endocr. Connect.* 9 (2), 101. <https://doi.org/10.1530/EC-19-0548>.
- Evangelista, S., Vazakidou, P., Koekoek, J., Heinzelmann, M.T., Lichtensteiger, W., Schlumpf, M., Tresguerres, J.A.F., Linillos-Pradillo, B., van Duursen, M.B.M., Lamoree, M.H., Leonards, P.E.G., 2024. High throughput LC-MS/MS method for steroid hormone analysis in rat liver and plasma – unraveling methodological challenges. *Talanta* 266, 124981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TALANTA.2023.124981>.
- Fenichel, P., Chevalier, N., Brucker-Davis, F., 2013. Bisphenol A: an endocrine and metabolic disruptor. *Ann. Endocrinol.* 74 (3), 211–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANDO.2013.04.002>.
- Firdessa, R., Oelschlaeger, T.A., Moll, H., 2014. Identification of multiple cellular uptake pathways of polystyrene nanoparticles and factors affecting the uptake: relevance for drug delivery systems. *Eur. J. Cell Biol.* 93 (8–9), 323–337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EJCB.2014.08.001>.
- Frenzilli, G., Martorell-Ribera, J., Bernardeschi, M., Scarcelli, V., Jönsson, E., Diano, N., Moggio, M., Guidi, P., Sturve, J., Asker, N., 2021. Bisphenol A and bisphenol S induce endocrine and chromosomal alterations in Brown Trout. *Front. Endocrinol.* 12, 161. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FENDO.2021.645519/BIBTEX>.
- Fuchs, A.K., Syrovets, T., Haas, K.A., Loos, C., Musyanovych, A., Mailänder, V., Landfester, K., Simmet, T., 2016. Carboxyl- and amino-functionalized polystyrene nanoparticles differentially affect the polarization profile of M1 and M2 macrophage subsets. *Biomaterials* 85, 78–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMATERIALS.2016.01.064>.
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J.R., Law, K.L., 2017. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci. Adv.* 3 (7) https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIADV.1700782/SUPPL_FILE/1700782_SM.PDF.
- Haddadi, A., Kessabi, K., Boughammoura, S., Rhouma, M. Ben, Mlouka, R., Banni, M., Messaoudi, I., 2022. Exposure to microplastics leads to a defective ovarian function and change in cytoskeleton protein expression in rat. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 29 (23), 34594–34606. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-021-18218-3/FIGURES/7>.
- Hilscherova, K., Jones, P.D., Gracia, T., Newsted, J.L., Zhang, X., Sanderson, J.T., Yu, R. M.K., Wu, R.S.S., Giesy, J.P., 2004. Assessment of the effects of chemicals on the expression of ten steroidogenic genes in the H295R cell line using real-time PCR. *Toxicol. Sci.* 81 (1), 78–89. <https://doi.org/10.1093/TOXSCI/KFH191>.
- Hirai, H., Takada, H., Ogata, Y., Yamashita, R., Mizukawa, K., Saha, M., Kwan, C., Moore, C., Gray, H., Laursen, D., Zettler, E.R., Farrington, J.W., Reddy, C.M., Peacock, E.E., Ward, M.W., 2011. Organic micropollutants in marine plastics debris from the open ocean and remote and urban beaches. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 62 (8), 1683–1692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2011.06.004>.
- Imhof, H.K., Ivleva, N.P., Schmid, J., Niessner, R., Laforsch, C., 2013. Contamination of beach sediments of a subalpine lake with microplastic particles. *Curr. Biol.* 23 (19), R867–R868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CUB.2013.09.001>.
- Inkiewicz-Stepniak, I., Tajber, L., Behan, G., Zhang, H., Radomski, M.W., Medina, C., Santos-Martinez, M.J., 2018. The role of mucin in the toxicological impact of polystyrene nanoparticles. *Materials (Basel, Switzerland)* 11 (5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/MA11050724>.
- Jenner, L.C., Rotchell, J.M., Bennett, R.T., Cowen, M., Tentzeris, V., Sadofsky, L.R., 2022. Detection of microplastics in human lung tissue using µFTIR spectroscopy. *Sci. Total Environ.* 831, 154907 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCIOTOTENV.2022.154907>.
- Jin, H., Ma, T., Sha, X., Liu, Z., Zhou, Y., Meng, X., Chen, Y., Han, X., Ding, J., 2021. Polystyrene microplastics induced male reproductive toxicity in mice. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 401 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2020.123430>.
- Jovanović, P., Žorić, L., Stefanović, I., Džunić, B., Djordjević-Jocić, J., Radenković, M., Jovanović, M., 2010. Lactate dehydrogenase and oxidative stress activity in primary open-angle glaucoma aqueous humour. *Bosn. J. Basic Med. Sci.* 10 (1), 83. <https://doi.org/10.17305/BJBMS.2010.2743>.
- Kannan, K., Vimalkumar, K., 2021. A review of human exposure to microplastics and insights into microplastics as obesogens. *Front. Endocrinol.* 12 <https://doi.org/10.3389/FENDO.2021.724989>.
- Kawagoshi, Y., Fujita, Y., Kishi, I., Fukunaga, I., 2003. Estrogenic chemicals and estrogenic activity in leachate from municipal waste landfill determined by yeast two-hybrid assay. *J. Environ. Monit.* 5 (2), 269–274. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B210962J>.
- Kinnear, C., Moore, T.L., Rodriguez-Lorenzo, L., Rothen-Rutishauser, B., Petri-Fink, A., 2017. Form follows function: nanoparticle shape and its implications for nanomedicine. *Chem. Rev.* 117 (17), 11476–11521. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.CHEMREV.7B00194>.
- Law, K.L., Morét-Ferguson, S.E., Goodwin, D.S., Zettler, E.R., Deforce, E., Kukulka, T., Proskurowski, G., 2014. Distribution of surface plastic debris in the eastern pacific ocean from an 11-year data set. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (9), 4732–4738. https://doi.org/10.1021/ES4053076/SUPPL_FILE/ES4053076_SI_002.AVI.
- Lee, A.J., Cai, M.X., Thomas, P.E., Conney, A.H., Zhu, B.T., 2003a. Characterization of the oxidative metabolites of 17β-estradiol and Estrone formed by 15 selectively expressed human cytochrome P450 isoforms. *Endocrinology* 144 (8), 3382–3398. <https://doi.org/10.1210/EN.2003-0192>.
- Lee, H.J., Chattopadhyay, S., Gong, E.Y., Ahn, R.S., Lee, K., 2003b. Antiandrogenic effects of bisphenol A and nonylphenol on the function of androgen receptor. *Toxicol. Sci.* 75 (1), 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1093/TOXSCI/KFG150>.
- Leslie, H.A., van Velzen, M.J.M., Brandsma, S.H., Vethaak, A.D., Garcia-Vallejo, J.J., Lamoree, M.H., 2022. Discovery and quantification of plastic particle pollution in human blood. *Environ. Int.* 163, 107199 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVIINT.2022.107199>.
- Lesniak, A., Salvati, A., Santos-Martinez, M.J., Radomski, M.W., Dawson, K.A., Åberg, C., 2013. Nanoparticle adhesion to the cell membrane and its effect on nanoparticle uptake efficiency. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (4), 1438–1444. https://doi.org/10.1021/JA309812Z/SUPPL_FILE/JA309812Z_S1_001.PDF.
- Li, J., Green, C., Reynolds, A., Shi, H., Rotchell, J.M., 2018. Microplastics in mussels sampled from coastal waters and supermarkets in the United Kingdom. *Environ. Pollut.* 241, 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2018.05.038>.
- Li, C., Ho, K., Tang, D., 2022. Effects of pH and Temperature on the Leaching of Di(2-Ethylhexyl) Phthalate and Di-n-butyl Phthalate from Microplastics in Simulated Marine Environment. <https://doi.org/10.33263/BRIACI33.269>.

- Li, Y., Tao, L., Wang, Q., Wang, F., Li, G., Song, M., 2023. Potential health impact of microplastics: a review of environmental distribution, human exposure, and toxic effects. *Environ. Health* 1 (4), 249–257. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ENVHEALTH.3C00052>.
- Liu, L., Liu, B., Zhang, B., Ye, Y., Jiang, W., 2022. Polystyrene micro(nano)plastics damage the organelles of RBL-2H3 cells and promote MOAP-1 to induce apoptosis. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 438, 129550 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2022.129550>.
- Lubos, E., Loscalzo, J., Handy, D.E., 2011. Glutathione Peroxidase-1 in health and disease: from molecular mechanisms to therapeutic opportunities. *Antioxid. Redox Signal.* 15 (7), 1957. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ARS.2010.3586>.
- Meeker, J.D., Ferguson, K.K., 2014. Urinary phthalate metabolites are associated with decreased serum testosterone in men, women, and children from NHANES 2011–2012. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* 99 (11), 4346–4352. https://doi.org/10.1210/JC.2014-2555/SUPPL_FILE/JC-14-2555.PDF.
- Michishita, S., Gibble, C., Tubbs, C., Felton, R., Gjeltema, J., Lang, J., Finkelstein, M., 2023. Microplastic in northern anchovies (*Engraulis mordax*) and common murex (*Uria aadgale*) from the Monterey Bay, California USA - insights into prevalence, composition, and estrogenic activity. *Environ. Pollut.* 316, 120548 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2022.120548>.
- Miller, W.L., Auchus, R.J., 2019. The “backdoor pathway” of androgen synthesis in human male sexual development. *PLoS Biol.* 17 (4) <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PBIO.3000198>.
- Mintinig, S.M., Löder, M.G.J., Primpke, S., Gerds, G., 2019. Low numbers of microplastics detected in drinking water from ground water sources. *Sci. Total Environ.* 648, 631–635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2018.08.178>.
- Noyola-Martínez, N., Halhali, A., Barrera, D., 2019. Steroid hormones and pregnancy. *Gynecol. Endocrinol.* 35 (5), 376–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09513590.2018.1564742>.
- OECD, 2018. Revised Guidance Document 150 on Standardised Test Guidelines for Evaluating Chemicals for Endocrine Disruption, 150. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304741-EN>.
- OECD, 2023. Test No. 456: H295R Steroidogenesis Assay, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals. OECD Publishing Paris. Section, 4.
- Oliveira, J., Belchior, A., da Silva, V.D., Rotter, A., Petrovski, Ž., Almeida, P.L., Lourenço, N.D., Gaudêncio, S.P., 2020. Marine environmental plastic pollution: mitigation by microorganism degradation and recycling valorization. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 1007. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMARS.2020.567126/BIBTEX>.
- Paluselli, A., Fauvel, V., Galgani, F., Sempéré, R., 2019. Phthalate release from plastic fragments and degradation in seawater. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53 (1), 166–175. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.EST.8B05083/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/ES-2018-05083Q.0004.JPEG>.
- Paris, F., Balaguer, P., Térouanne, B., Servant, N., Lacoste, C., Cravedi, J.P., Nicolas, J.C., Sultan, C., 2002. Phenylphenols, biphenols, bisphenol-A and 4-tert-octylphenol exhibit α and β estrogen activities and antiandrogen activity in reporter cell lines. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 193 (1–2), 43–49. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0303-7207\(02\)00094-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0303-7207(02)00094-1).
- Peng, Y., Wang, J., Wu, C., 2019. Determination of endocrine disruption potential of bisphenol A alternatives in food contact materials using in vitro assays: state of the art and future challenges. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 67 (46), 12613–12625. https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.JAFC.9B01543/ASSET/IMAGES/MEDIUM/JF-2019-01543F_0003.GIF.
- Ragusa, A., Svelato, A., Santacroce, C., Catalano, P., Notarstefano, V., Carnevali, O., Papa, F., Rongioletti, M.C.A., Baiocco, F., Draghi, S., D’Amore, E., Rinaldo, D., Matta, M., Giorgini, E., 2021. Placenta: first evidence of microplastics in human placenta. *Environ. Int.* 146, 106274 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVI.2020.106274>.
- Rejman, J., Oberle, V., Zuhorn, I.S., Hoekstra, D., 2004. Size-dependent internalization of particles via the pathways of clathrin- and caveolae-mediated endocytosis. *Biochem. J.* 377, 159–169.
- Robinson, D.P., Klein, S.L., 2012. Pregnancy and pregnancy-associated hormones alter immune responses and disease pathogenesis. *Horm. Behav.* 62 (3), 263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.YHBEH.2012.02.023>.
- Rogers, J.M., Denison, M.S., 2000. Recombinant cell bioassays for endocrine disruptors: development of a stably transfected human ovarian cell line for the detection of estrogenic and anti-estrogenic chemicals - PubMed. *In Vitro Mol. Toxicol.* 13 (1), 67–82.
- Ruan, Y., Zhong, Z., Liu, X., Li, Z., Li, J., Sun, L., Sen, H., 2023. Correlation between cellular uptake and cytotoxicity of polystyrene micro/nanoplastics in HeLa cells: a size-dependent matter. *PLoS One* 18 (8). <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0289473>.
- Rubin, B.S., 2011. Bisphenol A: an endocrine disruptor with widespread exposure and multiple effects. *J. Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 127 (1–2), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JSBMB.2011.05.002>.
- Saenen, N.D., Witters, M.S., Hantoro, I., Tejada, I., Ethirajan, A., Van Belleghem, F., Smeets, K., 2023. Polystyrene microplastics of varying sizes and shapes induce distinct redox and mitochondrial stress responses in a Caco-2 monolayer. *Antioxidants* 12 (3), 739. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANTIOX12030739>.
- Satoh, K., Ohyama, K., Aoki, N., Iida, M., Nagai, F., 2004. Study on anti-androgenic effects of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE), bisphenol F diglycidyl ether (BFDGE) and their derivatives using cells stably transfected with human androgen receptor, AR-EcoScreen. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 42 (6), 983–993. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FCT.2004.02.011>.
- Schiffer, L., Barnard, L., Baranowski, E.S., Gilligan, L.C., Taylor, A.E., Arlt, W., Shackleton, C.H.L., Storbeck, K.H., 2019. Human steroid biosynthesis, metabolism and excretion are differentially reflected by serum and urine steroid metabolomes: a comprehensive review. *J. Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 194 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JSBMB.2019.105439>.
- Schmidt, A., da Silva Brito, W.A., Singer, D., Mühl, M., Berner, J., Saadati, F., Wolff, C., Miebach, L., Wende, K., Bekeschus, S., 2023. Short- and long-term polystyrene nano- and microplastic exposure promotes oxidative stress and divergently affects skin cell architecture and Wnt/beta-catenin signaling. *Part. Fibre Toxicol.* 20 (1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S12989-023-00513-1>.
- Schrank, I., Trotter, B., Dummert, J., Scholz-Böttcher, B.M., Löder, M.G.J., Laforsch, C., 2019. Effects of microplastic particles and leaching additive on the life history and morphology of *Daphnia magna*. *Environ. Pollut.* 255, 113233 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2019.113233>.
- Semmouri, I., Vercauteren, M., Van Acker, E., Pequeur, E., Asselman, J., Janssen, C., 2022. Presence of microplastics in drinking water from different freshwater sources in Flanders (Belgium), an urbanized region in Europe. *Int. J. Food Contam.* 9 (1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40550-022-00091-8/FIGURES/6>.
- Stepanenko, A.A., Dmitrenko, V.V., 2015. Pitfalls of the MTT assay: direct and off-target effects of inhibitors can result in over/underestimation of cell viability. *Gene* 574 (2), 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GENE.2015.08.009>.
- Suleman, R., Amjad, A., Ismail, A., Javed, S., Ghafoor, U., Fahad, S., 2022. Impact of plastic bags usage in food commodities: an irreversible loss to environment. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.* 29 (33), 49483–49489. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-022-21091-3>.
- Tsuchiya, Y., Nakajima, M., Yokoi, T., 2005. Cytochrome P450-mediated metabolism of estrogens and its regulation in human. *Cancer Lett.* 227 (2), 115–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CANLET.2004.10.007>.
- Tulchinsky, D., Hobel, C.J., Yeager, E., Marshall, J.R., 1972. Plasma estrone, estradiol, estriol, progesterone, and 17-hydroxyprogesterone in human pregnancy. I. Normal pregnancy. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 112 (8), 1095–1100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378\(72\)90185-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378(72)90185-8).
- Ullerås, E., Ohlsson, Å., Oskarsson, A., 2008. Secretion of cortisol and aldosterone as a vulnerable target for adrenal endocrine disruption - screening of 30 selected chemicals in the human H295R cell model. *J. Appl. Toxicol.* 28 (8), 1045–1053. <https://doi.org/10.1002/JAT.1371>.
- van den Berg, A.E.T., Plantinga, M., Vethaak, D., Adriaans, K.J., Bol-Schoenmakers, M., Legler, J., Smit, J.J., Pieters, R.H.H., 2022. Environmentally weathered polystyrene particles induce phenotypical and functional maturation of human monocyte-derived dendritic cell. *J. Immunotoxicol.* 19 (1), 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1547691X.2022.2143968>.
- Vandesompele, J., De Preter, K., Pattyn, F., Poppe, B., Van Roy, N., De Paepe, A., Speleman, F., 2002. Accurate normalization of real-time quantitative RT-PCR data by geometric averaging of multiple internal control genes. *Genome Biol.* 3 (7), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/GB-2002-3-7-RESEARCH0034/COMMENTS>.
- Wiesinger, H., Wang, Z., Hellweg, S., 2021. Deep dive into plastic monomers, additives, and processing aids. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (13), 9339–9351. https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.EST.1C00976/ASSET/IMAGES/MEDIUM/ESI1C00976_0005.GIF.
- World Health Organization, The International Labour Organisation, & The United Nations Environment Programme, 2002. Global Assessment of the State-of-the-Science of Endocrine Disruptors.
- Wozniak, A.L., Bulayeva, N.N., Watson, C.S., 2005. Xenoestrogens at picomolar to nanomolar concentrations trigger membrane estrogen receptor- α -mediated Ca²⁺ fluxes and prolactin release in GH3/B6 pituitary tumor cells. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 113 (4), 431. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP.7505>.
- Yan, L., Yu, Z., Lin, P., Qiu, S., He, L., Wu, Z., Ma, L., Gu, Y., He, L., Dai, Z., Zhou, C., Hong, P., Li, C., 2023. Polystyrene nanoplastics promote the apoptosis in Caco-2 cells induced by okadaic acid more than microplastics. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 249, 114375 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOENV.2022.114375>.
- Yates, J., Deeney, M., Rolker, H.B., White, H., Kalamatianou, S., Kadiyala, S., 2021. A systematic scoping review of environmental, food security and health impacts of food system plastics. *Nat. Food* 2 (2), 80–87. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00221-z>.
- Zhang, M., Shi, J., Huang, Q., Xie, Y., Wu, R., Zhong, J., Deng, H., 2022. Multi-omics analysis reveals size-dependent toxicity and vascular endothelial cell injury induced by microplastic exposure in vivo and in vitro. *Environ. Sci. Nano* 9 (2), 663–683. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EN01067K>.
- Zwart, N., Andringa, D., de Leeuw, W.J., Kojima, H., Iida, M., Houtman, C.J., de Boer, J., Kool, J., Lamore, M.H., Hamers, T., 2017. Improved androgen specificity of AR-EcoScreen by CRISPR based glucocorticoid receptor knockout. *Toxicol. in Vitro* 45, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIV.2017.08.004>.